

FORMS OF CONDUCTING INFORMATION WARFARE IN SOCIAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

In a globalized world, the laws and methods of warfare have also changed. This article explains that war is being waged not only in real life, but also in the virtual arena, and social networks play an important role in waging war.

Keywords: Information war, information, Internet, security, social network.

ФОРМЫ ВЕДЕНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ ВОЙНЫ В СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ СЕТЯХ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В глобализированном мире изменились и законы и методы ведения войны. В данной статье объясняется, что война ведется не только в реальной жизни, но и на виртуальной арене, и важную роль в ведении войны играют социальные сети.

Ключевые слова: Информационная война, информация, Интернет, безопасность, социальная сеть.

ИЖТИМОЙ ТАРМОҚЛАРДА АХБОРОТ УРУШИНИ ОЛИБ БОРИШНИНГ ШАКЛЛАРИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Глобаллашган дунёда уруш қонунлари ва усуллари ҳам ўзгарди. Ушбу мақолада дунёда уруш нафақат реал ҳаётда, балки виртуал майдонда ҳам олиб борилаётганлиги, урушларни олиб боришда ижтимоий тармоқлар муҳим рол ўйнаётганлиги ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Ахборот уруши, ахборот, интернет, хавфсизлик, ижтимоий тармоқ.

The 21st century is the information age. Today, some countries have proven experimentally through data that it is possible to capture the mind of any country without weapons and kill it. Wherever people go, they are trapped by information. Wherever there is a society, wherever there is a state, there is a constant information attack. At first glance, we have seen that the information heard and absorbed by the mass media can lead to the outbreak of unarmed war in a small society, state, or even the whole world.

There is a famous old proverb: "When balls speak, pens are silent."⁸⁸ Now this rule has lost its force, and the phrase has become a beautiful expression - the balls make a loud noise when they are buzzing, the pen is never silent. In any case, when a temporary ceasefire has been declared in the war zone and the search for the dead continues, it is appropriate to talk about losses on the information front. War on the information front follows almost the same rules. Here too, uniform management, tactics and even special "weapons", knowledge and skills, technology are required.

According to experts, in the fight against information, high-precision information resources should have a compact system of programs for both active and passive protection. Enemy air defense and missile defense systems must not only protect, but also counter, information that can be actively and passively affected. For example, according to American military analyst Richard Shafransky, an "adversary" can be a political leader or anyone who opposes the leader's actions and goals, operating outside the country and inside the country, who controls the means of information warfare without projecting an "enemy image". If group members do not support the leader's goals during combat, internal information warfare (including propaganda, lies, acts of terrorism, and various rumors) can be used to sway them to the leaders' goals. considers as armed actions directed against any part of the knowledge system or assumptions⁸⁹.

⁸⁸Марк Туллий Цицерон. РЕЧИ В ДВУХ ТОМАХ. Том II (62—43 гг. до н. э.). Издание подготовили В. О. Горенштейн, М. Е. Грабарь-Пассек. Издательство Академии Наук СССР. Москва 1962. Перевод В. О. Горенштейна.

⁸⁹"Theory of Information Warfare", Preparing For 2020 by Colonel Richard Szafranski, USAF

Information warfare, in the language of war, here means the tactics and techniques of war, and in the language of information, these and manipulation technologies should be introduced into the public opinion. The mass media play the role of “munitions of war” in this war, and journalists and bloggers play the role of “shooters”. Simple lies are easy to expose, but artificial intelligence, using sophisticated software, to reveal that a fake is a fake, is beyond the capabilities of ordinary media. Therefore, to solve this problem, a team of experts with knowledge in various fields, special resources are needed.

Martin Libisky classifies 7 types of information warfare as follows:

Command and Control - This type of information warfare aims to cut off the communication between the commander and the executive.

Intelligence warfare involves gathering valuable information for offensive and defensive purposes.

Electronic warfare - In this type of information warfare, the goal is to destroy all electronic communications.

Psychological warfare - zombification of the population through propaganda and information.

Hacker warfare is the unauthorized access and use of various types of information. This includes email information, bank card information, personal files, correspondence, and more.

Economic warfare - information blockade (restriction of commercial activities) or information imperialism (political information attack)

Cyberwar - collection of computer data, monitoring of objects, attempts to destroy infrastructure based on information technology⁹⁰.

Throughout history, information has played a huge role in warfare. In the Middle Ages, the number of enemy troops, military power and other information were studied with the help of dervishes in the East and church monks in Europe. In the Middle Ages, spreading propaganda with the help of special people in the territory of the enemy, forming a different opinion in the country was one of the important issues. With the development of science in the 19th century, the transmission of information also accelerated. For example, if we focus on the First World War era, the mass media caricatured the image of the enemy and made people hate them. During the battle, special leaflets calling for surrender were distributed to the enemy army and civilians.

During World War II and the Cold War, the Soviets, as a closed nation, reduced the enemy's ability to intervene. Therefore, a real intelligence war began between the West and the Soviets. The main power and function of spymasters was to transmit

⁹⁰M.C.Libicki «What is Information warfare» National Defense University W. 1995 P. 16.

secret information. If necessary, it was to weaken the state structure by carrying out propaganda. With the development of technology, the spread and amount of information has also increased. Our world is starting to look like a big business. Culture has now become part of the information and propaganda machine. In the political sense, the open struggle was played by radios, newspapers and books. During the Cold War, Western radio broadcasts were imported into the Soviet Union and promoted among the population.

In today's Internet age, the methodology of wars has not changed, only the means are changing. Newspapers, television and radio, which were powerful in their time, are the most convenient means of information in the context of globalization. The Internet has increasingly become a platform for social network companies, news agencies, as they say.

In our globalized world, the laws and methods of warfare have also changed. The world powers prefer to fight on the territory of the countries they are fighting, not on their own territory, and as a result, separatist and terrorist groups are emerging in the regions. In addition to their training camps and weapons depots, modern terrorists also have special cyber groups that conduct propaganda to channel information and propaganda to their advantage. In his research, A.V. Manoylo focuses on information attack - the distribution of specially selected and prepared information between different communities aimed at achieving political, economic, military or other strategic goals by influencing the citizens of the country, the authorities and the armed forces of the dependent and opposing side, and information materials and their own defines as the process of resisting such influence⁹¹. Of course, specially selected and prepared information is the basis for changing the opinion of the country's population in a positive or negative direction.

In today's world, war is being waged not only in real life, but also in the virtual space. The relevant offices and organizations of almost all countries are aware of this and have large-scale action plans in the information space and special agencies operating in this regard. However, with the development of the information space, more and more groups have joined the struggle to take their place or expand their position in this space.

In addition to various countries, large multinational companies, political groups, representatives of show business and finally terrorists joined the fight. Recently, ISIS terrorists have been demonstrating their "digital marketing" skills on social networks.

⁹¹Манойло А.В. "Информационные войны и психологические операции. Руководство к действию". - М.: Изд-во РАГС, 2019. - 125 с.

Until now, no radical or terrorist organization has been able to use social media as skillfully as ISIS. ISIS cyber soldiers have flooded Twitter and YouTube with their propaganda material. Facebook and Instagram did not escape their attention. These social networks are both propaganda and communication (coordinating) for ISIS. they also play the role of “military commissariat” to recruit new fighters. Even the famous Russian social network “Vkontakte” did not escape the attention of terrorists.

All this indicates that the world community is facing a very serious, well-organized and well-armed enemy. Based on this, it is necessary to take a more careful and serious approach to the infrastructure created by terrorists in the world information space, especially in its social network segment. The special services of countries fighting against terrorists have a difficult task of identifying and preventing terrorist infrastructure in the global information space. Some experts in the West believe that the fight against terrorists in social networks can be seen as a restriction of freedom of speech. We do not agree with this opinion, our special services should not only close the pages and official accounts created by terrorists in social networks, but also find the accounts of individual terrorists and their associates and stop their activities. Beheadings and sharing images on social media have nothing to do with freedom of speech and opinion. That is, with this opinion, I would like to mention that Google, Yahoo, Yandex and other search services have a special place. Thus, one of the most effective measures these services can take is to remove content related to terrorists and terrorist organizations from search results.

The "Arab Spring" that began in the Arab world showed the importance of social networks and their social and political life. The social network Twitter stood out especially in this area. This social network is the most popular tool currently available in the world for the rapid spread of information on the viral principle. In the West it is well known and used. The Arab Spring and the role of social media in it forced many countries to revise and adjust their information security policies. This is actually normal and expected. Five years have passed since the beginning of the Arab Spring, and now Twitter and other social networks have developed, increased the number of users, expanded and strengthened the possibilities of information dissemination.

Forecasting groups of institutions and organizations involved in this field in major countries certainly take all this into account when developing a national information security strategy. Countries that do not work in this area or do not have the personnel and capacity to do so are vulnerable to potential threats. Although some countries are trying to crack down on restricting access to major social networks from their own countries, this is becoming more and more difficult this year due to the growing and sophisticated proxy programs. According to the data of the State Statistics Committee, as of January 1, 2021, the number of subscribers connected to the Internet is about 20

million. established This indicator has increased by 21.9% compared to the same period last year⁹². Now it only takes a second for positive or negative information to appear on the global network. This information is related not only to national interests, security and sovereignty of the country, but also to the people living in this country. According to information, 1% of the employed population in Uzbekistan works in the information sector. However, this indicator is 4-5 % in the USSR, 5-6% in the EU, and 4% in Russia.

According to the expert, companies that manage many social networks can limit the activities of terrorists. For some reason this does not happen. When an external video is uploaded to a major video site like YouTube, the video is immediately blocked, but for some reason, ISIS performance footage uploaded to YouTube remains visible to viewers for a long time. World powers are creating and promoting their own social networking sites to ensure information security and influence people living in other countries. On average, 60-70 % of trending materials directed at the country are distributed through the Internet. About 8,000 negative materials were sent to “consumers” on social networks, more than 3,000 on the Internet, more than 500 on radio and 113 on television. 5,435 of the neutral information were distributed using social networks, 5,497 on the Internet, 2,258 on radio waves, and 4,637 on television. Information such as the above was distributed through social networks in the form of videos, respondents, bloggers’ materials, comments, etc.⁹³

To sum up, first of all, the information environment of today’s society has changed radically, modern information technologies have entered practically all fields, and people have become an integral part of information culture. Secondly, the increase in information resources due to the development of telecommunications and modern information technologies has created new information relations and forms of employment. Thirdly, in countries with advanced information and communication technologies, new information technologies and systems have become not only an integral part of society, but also a part of the daily life of individual citizens. These are, first of all, modern equipment used in mass media, Internet and various radio electronic systems (mobile communication, global high-definition transmission, wireless network and optical fiber cable used for data transmission). Fourth, the information age directly or indirectly affects all areas of human life. Thus, wars that have been waged for years are easily fought and won in the virtual space called the Internet. The Internet has been

⁹²<https://xs.uz/uzkr/post/ozbekistonda-internet-tarmogiga-ulangan-abonentlar-soni-malum-qilindi>

⁹³Ўзбекистон Республикаси Стратегик ва минтақалараро тадқиқотлар институти маълумотларидан. Мурожаат санаси: 20.02.2020 й.

waging a bloody war for decades in a very simple way. We must not forget that it is no longer profitable to wage war with brute force. Modern wars are fought on a virtual plane.

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